
THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN PROMOTING PEACE AND SOCIAL COHESION IN RURAL MINING AREAS OF INSIZA DISTRICT, ZIMBABWE

Dlamini, Thandeka Nomusa

Department of Social Sciences, Durban University of Technology, Durban, South Africa.

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ABSTRACT	KEY WORDS
<p>Women in Zimbabwe’s Insiza District have emerged as key agents in peacebuilding, particularly in response to violence and conflicts arising from artisanal mining activities in Wards 1 and 2. This study evaluates the effectiveness of the Emthonjeni Women's Forum (EWF) project, which established 12 peace committees comprising 120 women peacebuilders. The study area is characterized by high unemployment, subsistence farming, and the presence of illegal artisanal miners, leading to violent gang activity by groups such as the aMabhambadzi. These gangs have disrupted community life, eroded cultural norms, and undermined social cohesion through the use of force to seize gold and mining claims.</p> <p>The peace committees serve as community-driven mechanisms for conflict identification, analysis, and resolution. They implement prevention strategies, establish early warning systems, and facilitate dialogue to mitigate disputes. This research examines the role of women as strategic partners in the EWF’s Peacebuilding and Social Cohesion initiative, assessing how their interventions influence the resolution of everyday conflicts and the restoration of social harmony.</p> <p>Findings indicate that women’s involvement has strengthened community resilience, enhanced participatory conflict resolution, and contributed to the re-establishment of trust and cultural norms within affected areas. By highlighting women’s contributions, this study underscores their pivotal role in promoting sustainable peace in rural mining communities plagued by violence and lawlessness. The insights gained have implications for policy, community development programs, and the broader understanding of gendered approaches to peacebuilding in rural and resource-driven contexts.</p>	<p>Women peacebuilders, Peacebuilding, Social cohesion, Artisanal mining, Zimbabwe.</p>

Introduction

Women in Zimbabwe’s Insiza District have actively engaged in peacebuilding efforts to address the violence and conflicts stemming from artisanal mining activities in Wards 1 and 2. This study investigates the efficacy of the efforts of women who are part of the Emthonjeni Women's Forum (EWF) project, which established 12 peace

committees with 120 women peacebuilders. The area, characterized by high unemployment, subsistence farming, and illegal artisanal mining, has seen an influx of outsiders seeking gold, leading to the prevalence of violent gangsters known as aMabhambadzi. The unruly gangs have caused fear and disruption in the community, using force to grab gold and claims and contributing to the breakdown of cultural norms and the social fabric. The peace committees work with the community to identify and analyze conflicts, establish resolution platforms, evaluate prevention mechanisms, and establish early warning systems. This research assesses the impact of women as strategic partners in the EWF's Peacebuilding and Social Cohesion project, examining whether their work makes a difference in addressing everyday conflicts. This study aims to contribute to the understanding of women's roles in peacebuilding in rural mining communal areas affected by violence and lawlessness.

Research context

Emthonjeni Women's Forum (EWF) implemented the *women as strategic partners in peace building* project in Wards 1 and 2 of Insiza District, Matabeleland South in Zimbabwe.

The area is predominantly dry and susceptible to droughts as it falls under agricultural region 4, which is dry and arid. It receives an annual rainfall of approximately 58, 84 milliliters (2.32 inches) and is prone to periodic droughts. While animal ranching is the most suitable agricultural activity for the area, communities in Wards 1 and 2 tend to engage in subsistence farming and illegal artisanal mining because of high unemployment and dwindling crop production. Because of the rich gold reserves, Wards 1 and 2 have an influx of 'outsiders' flocking into the area in search of gold. The sheer number of artisanal miners and the general lack of the rule of law, which characterizes artisanal mining and gold panning in general, has given rise to all sorts of conflicts and violent activities in Insiza. In particular, the prevalence of violent gangsters armed with machetes (*pangas*) (known as *aMabhambadzi* in Insiza) has caused untold havoc in the area, resulting in mass fear among the communities. The unruly gangs use force to grab other miners' processed gold, the ore, or any claim that is suspected to have rich gold veins; they do not hesitate to maim or kill to access them (ICG, 2020; Mkodzongi, 2020; Smith, 2020). Furthermore, moral decadence and the breakdown of cultural norms have resulted in an increase in violent conflicts and dysfunction in families and the community.

Since 2020, the EWF has been working with women in these two volatile wards and has trained them in peace and conflict resolution. They established 12 peace committees in the two wards, with a total of 120 women peacebuilders. Local women in the two wards are involved in efforts to mitigate conflicts and violence that have plagued the area because of the increase in lawlessness and the breakdown of the social fabric in the community. Peace Committees are an integral part of the EWF program implemented in Wards 1 and 2 of the Insiza District. Their role is to jointly identify and analyze conflicts, establish and identify platforms for resolving such conflicts, evaluate conflict prevention and resolution mechanisms in their communities, and establish early warning systems for potential conflicts. Peace Committees are one of the peace infrastructures used by women in their peace-making efforts. Wards 1 and 2 are situated in a gold-rich area and, like other areas with artisanal mining, are not spared the chaos, conflicts, and violence associated with the presence of unruly machete gangs that have no regard for law and order, or indeed life. These two wards present a set of circumstances that might be different from other mining areas in the sense that the effects of lawlessness are not confined to the mining areas of the wards but also permeate their lives in their homes.

This research was carried out to assess the impact women were having in the area as strategic partners in the Peacebuilding and Social Cohesion project being implemented by EWF, in Wards 1 and 2 of Insiza District. The guiding question is whether the peace committees are making a difference in the way everyday conflicts are

addressed by both members of the peace committees and the community at large. The primary conclusion derived from the study was that the greater success and effectiveness of women in establishing peace within their communities was directly proportional to their moral authority rooted in a shared cultural understanding. Furthermore, it seems that women transcended patriarchal obstacles in these two wards, as men did not exhibit any negative attitudes towards their leadership in building peace within the communities. In contrast, the prevailing perception was that men, traditional leaders, and the police all considered them indispensable components of the peace infrastructure in the Insiza District.

Literature Review

Although women (along with children and the elderly) tend to be most affected by violent conflicts (Chitando, 2019; George & Soaki, 2020; Shepherd, 2020; UNSCR, 2000), it has long been acknowledged that they can play a crucial role in peace processes. The push to recognize and involve women in peace negotiations and peacebuilding activities has been ongoing for over two decades now. The United Nations Security Council Resolution (UNSCR) 1325 on Women, Peace and Security (WPS), affirms the “important role of women in the prevention and resolution of conflicts and peacebuilding” and the need for “their equal participation and full involvement in all efforts for the maintenance and promotion of peace and security” (UNSCR, 2000). The follow-up resolution (UNSCR, 2122) seeks to further focus on gender and conflict transition by listing methods that could be used to overcome the obstacles obstructing women’s participation in peacebuilding (George & Soaki, 2020). The resolution speaks about the importance of United Nations (UN) agencies’ “field mission visits” and “interactive meetings with local women and women’s organizations in the field” to “engage and support women’s leadership within civil society” (Shepherd, 2020; UNSCR, 2013).

The work done by women in Liberia, Ghana, and Kenya is just three examples of successful peacebuilding interventions carried out by women in Africa. In Liberia, women played a major albeit informal role in forcing warring parties to negotiate for genuine and long-lasting peace. Started in 2003 by Leymah Gbowee, a Christian lady, the women’s movement towards peace in Liberia soon became a force to be reckoned with. Gbowee was troubled by the violence in her country and the lackluster efforts to negotiate peace by various actors in the Liberian conflict. She gathered women from her church for peace prayers, which soon grew to include other denominations, as well as a movement called the Women in Peace Network. They were soon joined by Muslim women to form a united movement, the Women of Liberian Mass Action for Peace Campaign. With the increase of violence in April 2003, the women numbering between 2000 and 3000 decided to meet daily at the Monrovia fish market where they prayed, danced, sang, and chanted their demand;

“We want peace!” No More war!” (Daisy, 2008, as cited in Ouellet, 2013, p. 14). With no sign of the war abating, the women instituted a ban on sex and refused to sleep with their husbands until the war stopped. Soon after, the men joined their wives to pray for peace. During the peace talks that took place in Accra, Ghana, 300 women from Liberia, Ghana, and Sierra Leone surrounded the conference center where the negotiations were taking place to pressure the negotiators to come up with a genuine and lasting peace. During breaks, the women lobbied the parties and even the negotiators’ families back home to exert more pressure on them. When the talks reached an impasse, the women prevented delegates from leaving the conference room until an agreement was reached. When security tried to remove the women by force, they went to the extent of removing their clothes in front of the men to show their seriousness in seeking resolution. It is a great act of shaming for an older woman to strip in front of men, especially in public. A comprehensive peace agreement was eventually crafted, but the women’s

work did not stop there. They were involved in the reconciliation processes that followed. The UN requested that they advise troops on disarmament (Goyol, 2019; Hayner, 2007; Moran & Pitcher, 2004; Ouellet, 2013).

Similarly, women in Kenya have been instrumental in bringing peace to their communities. Perhaps the most prominent interventions are those in the Wajir District, spearheaded by the well-known peace activist, the late Dekha Ibrahim Abdi. After the 1992 Kenyan elections, massive violence broke out in the district, with looting, home invasions, highway robberies, and general lawlessness being the order of the day. When fights broke out among women in a market, some women, mostly of Somali descent, managed to resolve them.

Their success spurred them to deal with other conflicts in their communities. The women were able to convince clan elders to renounce violence and work towards peace. A Council of Elders for Peace was formed from the resultant efforts, and this was instrumental in stopping common inter-clan raids. The women also mobilized young people to form Youth for Peace Groups, which helped reduce violence among the youth. The women also took the initiative to dissuade militias from their violent lifestyles by working with many NGOs to offer them alternative sources of income. Various peace infrastructures were established in Wajir to sustain peace. As a result of sustained peacebuilding work spearheaded by women,

Wajir is now largely a peaceful place where conflicts are resolved nonviolently (Juma, 2000).

Although very few women in Zimbabwe are or have been involved in high-level peace processes (for instance, during the negotiations for the 2008 Government of National Unity, out of the six negotiators from the three parties involved, only one was a woman), they have actively participated in local-level peacebuilding activities. As has been argued by Schirch & Sewak (2005, p. 1), “Women’s involvement in peacebuilding is as old as their experience in violence”.

Many civil society organizations’ programs are underpinned by women’s participation, and women have been involved in successful peacebuilding at the local community level in many parts of Zimbabwe. For instance, Moyo-Nyoni and Kiyala (2022) discuss the peace work done by women in the Lupane District in collaboration with Grace To

Heal. Chitando (2019) focused on peacebuilding efforts by young women in Mashonaland

East, while Masunungure and Mbwirire (2016) presented a case study of women’s involvement in conflict resolution within the Salvation Army Church in Bindura, Mashonaland Central.

However, despite many similar success stories, women still face major stumbling blocks in their quest to participate in peace processes, especially in more formal processes at the national and regional levels. Some of these challenges include the patriarchal ideologies and values embedded in most African societies that tend to marginalize and minimize women’s contributions to important existential issues in the community, weak political will, and limited awareness of UNSCR 1325, especially among rural women; lack of critical mass of women’s voices and experts in African peace and security; shortage of dialogue, collaboration, and strategic networking among women’s organizations; and economic factors that force women to focus on trying to make a living rather than long-term peacebuilding (Chitando, 2019; Machakanja, 2016). Furthermore, UNSCR 1820 acknowledges persistent violence and intimidation as barriers to women’s effective participation in peacebuilding initiatives.

Research objectives

This study examined the usefulness of having women as strategic partners in peacebuilding and social cohesion in two wards of the Insiza District. The objective was to investigate the role of women in constructing peace within their communities and to assess the efficacy of the knowledge and abilities acquired from the diverse peacebuilding training programs provided by the EWF. What influence, if any, has the training of women and the

formation of peace committees had on reducing gender-based conflict and violence, particularly within the two wards? Are there any noteworthy instances in which the resolution of disputes or the alleviation of violence can be ascribed to the intervention of women?

Methodology

This study used a qualitative research approach to understand the nature of gendered violence and conflicts, as it aimed to understand not only the kinds but also the ways in which different groupings in the communities were affected by them. Data was collected through indepth interviews with key informants (KI) and focus group discussions (FGDs). Purposive sampling was used in this study, which allowed for the selection of relevant individuals with knowledge or experience of the study subject (Leavy, 2017). Seventy-four participants (44 females and 30 males) were selected for this study. FGDs participants were selected from the Emthonjeni Women's Forum (EWF) participants and community members in Wards 1 and 2. Participants were identified and mobilized through EWF structures. Key Informants included the peace committee leaders (all females), traditional leaders, councilors from the two wards, the District Development Coordinator's office, the Zimbabwe Republic Police, and the Women's Affairs Ministry officials. FGDs for men and women were conducted separately to allow for greater freedom of speech and reduce the undue influence of one group on another. Five female and four male FGDs were conducted, and the number of participants varied between six and twelve per group. In compliance with research ethics norms, informed consent was obtained from the participants after they were briefed on the purpose and objectives of the research. In addition, the participants' contributions were anonymized to protect their identities.

The discussions and interviews were audio-recorded, and notes were taken by two research assistants. Most of the key informant interviews were conducted in the local language, and the transcripts were later translated into English. The findings were derived through thematic analysis, which involved a manual coding process in which the researchers closely read the transcripts and assigned codes to portions deemed significant to the study. Similar codes were merged into new codes, while others were disconfirmed. During the interviews and focus group discussions, certain recurring themes emerged, which were subsequently utilized as the initial themes upon which the remaining themes were developed by recognizing the patterns across the identified codes. General themes included interventions carried out by peace committees, challenges faced, and the impact of the peace committees on community conflicts, along with specific examples of each.

Assessing the effectiveness of the women's peacebuilding efforts

The "Women as Strategic Partners in Peacebuilding" program is an initiative implemented by EWF in Wards 1 and 2 of Insiza. EWF primarily focuses on working with women, advocating for them, and campaigning on their behalf. The organization is concerned with the mitigation of all forms of gender-based violence, which is prevalent and sometimes intractable in communities with artisanal mining. A small segment of men participates in EWF activities, especially in peace committees (PCs). Peace committees appear to be the flagship activity for this program, with each village having its own PC consisting of approximately 10 to 12 individuals, which are coordinated by a ward PC. The composition of village PCs varies slightly from village to village, but generally includes women, men, and villageheads. Some, such as Gangabezi, consist only of men because of the nature of the conflicts in the village and the community's chosen response to them. The ward PCs are exclusively female, which means that the leadership and function of village PCs are under the guidance of women, even in those predominantly comprised of men. At the time of the research, the PCs had been active for approximately two years.

Types of interventions carried out by peace committees

Public violence

By default, all peace committees address problems caused by outsiders within their villages, such as acts of violence and theft at shopping centers or in the village itself. However, it should be noted that their interventions do not extend to mining areas where roving machete gangs are located and lawlessness reaches its peak. All respondents reported that shopping centers had become venues for fights, mostly between outsiders and locals, but also among locals when people were drunk. It is important to mention that participants felt that the presence of peace committees helped reduce the incidents of violence at shopping centers.

In the evenings, we hear all sorts of languages that we don't understand, and we don't even know where these people stay. We sat down and selected a committee, it is the one that helped reduce the amount of violence in our community, because now people are no longer allowed to carry machetes, axes or knobkerries near the shopping center. If they see you carrying any of these, they will immediately confiscate them. If you try to resist, the committee members will take you to a designated place and give you corporal punishment (Gangabezi, village, female FGD).

Participants also noted that bottle stores [bars] and night clubs that had been violating their closing times and allowing underage drinking, thus encouraging violence from drunken youths, had largely been brought under control. As per one peace committee respondent,

“Even at the shops there is violence because we have been called several times to order the shop owners to close on time because when they close late at night these young boys get drunk and when they are drunk, they go around insulting adults” (Vusisizwe village, peace committee member).

To further curb the hooliganism caused by drunk youth at night, all those under the age of 18 are no longer allowed to be at the shops after 7 p.m. Peace committees patrol the shops after this time to ensure that no underage youth are loitering. Both villagers and businesspeople agreed that they would not be entertained in their shops. Young men who insult villagers when drunk at night on their way home have the peace committee following them home the next day to admonish them. All participants agreed that there had been a significant reduction in such incidents, and PCs had gained respect even among offenders, who no longer acted with impunity. According to the Ministry of Women's Affairs official, When the peace committees had just started, communities used to complain about shops and bars that were open late. They felt that this caused an increase in crime rates. The peace committee has helped there because they sat down as villages, up to ward level and came up with their own rules to say we don't want such a thing, shops must close early (Ministry of Women's Affairs KI)

A peace committee respondent explained, “... Even our young children were flocking to the shops [at night], but now the peace committee has set a rule that by 7 p.m., even if they are 18 years old, they must go home. They know that there is a peace committee [that monitors compliance]” (Ukuzwisisa village, peace committee). They further explained how they had managed to bring back a sense of decorum among the unruly young men, When these boys got drunk, they would go about shouting insults at adults or call you, ‘hey so and so's mother...’ and just insult you with unprintable insults in public for no apparent reason. But now we are able to call that person and summon him to the villagehead's court and reprimand him there. Sometimes, we call them aside during their soccer matches and talk to them about their wayward behavior (Ukuzwisisa Village Peace Committee, FGD).

One exception was Theleka in Ward 2, where most of the businesses were run by people who were not from that community, and where most of the outsiders resided because of the availability of rented accommodation

(especially rooms behind the shops, which is illegal). The men at Marubamba spoke about a recent ‘operation *dudula*’ (eviction of those illegally renting such structures) at Theleka but indicated that the evictees had all returned within a short space of time. They intimated that they were now hesitant to carry out another operation for fear of being victimized by these people, who seemed to act with impunity with the support of some locals who benefited from the rentals.

People no longer respect the villageheads; they do as they please, yet respecting our traditional leaders is important. If you live in a certain village, the villagehead will be like your parent. If you evict people, these tenants [from illegal accommodation], you will be in danger because they will look for you and beat you up or kill you. Even if you tell the villagehead, they will know who told them because you would have evicted them before (Marubamba village, male FGD).

Most of the peace committees in both wards managed to reduce or completely ban the carrying of machetes and other weapons, including catapults, in public spaces such as shopping centers. To enforce these rules, some resort to the use of force. Almost all the discussion groups mentioned the Gangabezi village PC as having the most success, and some longed to have the same success in their villages as Gangabezi. This PC is composed predominantly of young men, with a few women who are members of the neighborhood watch police or villageheads. In Gangabezi village, those who disobey the order not to carry weapons around the shopping area are taken to a shed used for public meetings and subjected to corporal punishments. This practice has been employed numerous times to send a strong message beyond the village, emphasizing the importance of adhering to the rules. As a result, the number of individuals who willfully disobeyed decreased.

However, from a peacebuilding perspective, the use of violence to maintain peace poses a dilemma. When is it acceptable to use violence to maintain peace? Is peace truly maintained when it is achieved through violence? Does the use of violence not perpetuate a culture of violence rather than fostering a culture of peace in the community? Moreover, the long-term sustainability of peace remains uncertain. This situation may be seen as a prime example of Galtung's (1969) negative peace, which refers to the absence of direct violence rather than positive peace, and is characterized by the presence of social justice or the absence of indirect and structural violence.

Nevertheless, given the unruly nature of artisanal miners, the use of force to maintain peace for the benefit of the community may be justified. However, the higher number of men than women on this committee may have influenced the approach chosen by the Peace Committee. In Gangabezi, women seemed content to allow young men to take the lead and were not actively participating in the same manner as women in other Peace Committees. The reasons for this group's divergence from the others remain unclear; one can hypothesize that the higher proportion of male participants may have influenced the female participants to revert to a patriarchal paradigm of deferring to male leadership.

In Theleka, there was a noticeable difference in the success rate of the interventions depending on whether the participants were from within or outside the two wards. According to the respondents, intervening in Theleka conflicts posed significant risks, as they feared being targeted by the individuals involved.

Safeguarding the girl child

Several examples of young girls rescued by the actions of the PCs from the decadence of gold money were referenced by some participants. Several respondents indicated that artisanal miners, both outsiders and locals, placed the girl child in danger by luring them with gifts such as mobile phones, airtime, and food. This has resulted

in teenage pregnancies and school dropouts. These males would go to the extent of visiting girls, even at school, thus disrupting their education. For instance, one of the key informants from the District Development Coordinator's office referred to a situation at Tshazi Secondary School (Ward 1) where artisanal miners were in the habit of disrupting lessons by calling schoolgirls out of class during lessons. School authorities failed to deal with this situation and had to call upon the local peace committee for assistance. According to the officer, the PC had been able to bring this to a stop, as the male artisanal miners were no longer visiting the school. The FGD at Vusisizwe related two incidents of 14-year-old girls with whom they had worked and assisted in regaining a sense of normalcy: one of the girls eloped, but they managed to take her home and back to school again. The Marubamba villagehead also referred to this eloped 14-year-old when asked about the work of the PC in their areas.

According to the Vusisizwe PC,

We had a case of a young girl who had dropped out of school and eloped. As the peace committee, we realised that it was not right for a 14-year-old girl to be married when she should have been in school. The family with whom she eloped were hesitant to take her back home. We told them that a 14-year-old should be in school. We took the child back and ensured that she returned to school. We had another 14-year-old orphan who, when reprimanded, ran away and slept by the gravesite. Her aunts came to us [for help]; we told them to let us know when she returned home. Fortunately, the girl went to stay at this other lady's store, so we asked her about her problems. We told her that we would follow her to

'Seven to Seven' with a whip because at her age she should be at school [Seven to Seven is a nightclub at the district center where she apparently would go dancing]. She stopped going there as well as sleeping in the graveyard. Now she is alright; we meet her sometimes fetching water, but unfortunately, she has never returned to school. However, she returned to being a normal child. Now, they can even send her to the shops. Before, they could never send her; if they sent her to the shops, she would never come back with the change (Vusisizwe PC). In the second case, we see the cultural default of corporal punishment for every disciplinary issue. However, in this case, it only ended in threats. This case is indicative of possible deeper mental and psychological issues that might have required a different intervention or approach to address the causes of her antisocial behavior. Children were not spared from the adverse effects of the social ills brought about by the prevailing environment. Dropping out of school in the first year of high school, early marriages, and teen pregnancies, were some of the issues the peace committees had to deal with

(Ngwenya, et al, 2024)

Intervening in family conflicts

Participants reported that PCs had intervened in some family conflicts with a degree of success. The villageheads at Marubamba mentioned the incident of a man who had terrorized his wife and child, which the peace committee had successfully addressed. This similar incident was narrated by the Ward 1 councilor as follows,

There is a man who used to beat his wife, and he ended up locking her in the house. I am not sure how the peace committee heard about it: they went to the homestead, but the man refused to entertain them. They reported to the police and advised them on how to arrest the man. As we speak, the man is in prison, and the wife and child are in the hospital because they had been badly injured by the man. The parents of this couple did not know what was happening, but the peace committee found out somehow and worked with the police to resolve the situation (Ward 1 Councilor, KII).

A lady who had been assisted by the peace committee to resolve a conflict between her husband and her brother-in-law, which had soured relations in the whole family had this to say,

The ongoing conflict was exacerbated by the fact that even community members had grown more concerned about it. Tensions escalated to the point where even my mother-in-law, who had a strong attachment to her youngest son, became involved. Our families had stopped communicating, and visits between relatives had ceased. This situation persisted for a long period. Fortunately, the peace committee provided invaluable assistance in resolving the conflict, as previous attempts by the clan and villagehead had proven futile. The committee promptly addressed the issue, utilizing their analytical skills to identify where each party had erred. Consequently, the family forgave one another and resolved the conflict amicably. Now, if disputes arise, the family can address them peacefully and harmoniously. My mother-in-law has resumed visiting us, and we reciprocate by visiting my brother-in-law. The peace committee is an invaluable resource as it is swift to assist and maintain confidentiality, ensuring that issues are not discussed in other circles. Without their intervention, the conflict might still be ongoing, as people had ceased to care about one another.

During the interview conducted at this lady's homestead, an older lady was observed entering the homestead and having a brief conversation with the participant. It later transpired that this was the mother-in-law, thus validating this narrative. The peace committees' success in addressing social issues, especially with the youth, can be attributed to their moral authority as mothers and their ability to foster open and respectful dialogue among all parties involved.

Stakeholders' view of the program

Overall, the program was well regarded in the community and by other stakeholders, such as the DDC, Ministry of Women's Affairs, and Zimbabwe Republic Police (ZRP), who had participated in the program's activities. According to an officer at the DDC, the program had helped bring many cases of violence to the surface, some of which had already been addressed. In her opinion, even men were now confident enough to report if they were being abused by their wives, instead of just bottling it up. It is also worth mentioning that there were other organizations working with women and girls in the same area, so attribution might be an issue; however, these were mentioned once by the men's FGD at Thandanani in Ward 1. These were mentioned in the context of a complaint by men that they felt left behind, since all organizations working in the area focused on women and girls only. Officers from the ZRP acknowledged the importance and effectiveness of the work of the PCs with whom they claimed to work closely. According to them, the Thandanani PC (which covers the Mahole Business Center, the central point of the two wards) was always the first on the scene and alerted the police of the violent incidents. Whenever they referred victims to the police station in Filabusi (the Insiza District Center), they followed up to ascertain what action the police were taking.

According to the officer from the Ministry of Women's Affairs, PCs are an important part of the peacebuilding work in Wards 1 and 2. As a Ministry, they rely on them to gauge the state of conflict and violence in the wards. The officer further reported that there had been a positive and tangible transformation within the wards due to the work of the peace committees. She provided an example of a situation in which a PC assisted in resolving a brewing conflict between parents and their school-going children: There was once a time when the children learned about child abuse at school; they went back to their homes and were now threatening to report their parents to the police for 'child abuse' whenever the parents tried to discipline them. It had reached a stage where parents no longer reprimanded their children for fear of being reported, and the children felt free to do whatever they wanted.

The PC was able to assist both the children and parents in finding a workable balance between the two extremes. The reference was to the use of corporal punishment as a form of discipline. This appears to be the default practice in most homes in this area.

The officer reported that from the beginning, the villagers participated in the formulation of the rules and principles by which they wanted their communities to live. This early buy-in by the communities is perhaps one of the major contributing factors to the success and wide acceptance of the PCs.

Men's views of women as peacebuilders

Most male FGD participants spoke positively about the role of women in building peace in their communities. They affirmed the positive role of women in PCs across community formations. This was best expressed by three of the male participants, Before Emthonjeni came, there were many conflicts and insults in the area, but with the arrival of Emthonjeni, we now have peace because of their teachings. Young people did not appreciate the work of Emthonjeni, but because of their teachings, the children who care to listen are being helped (Marubamba village, male FGD, Ward 2).

...But since the formation of the peace committee [in Gangabezi village], it is now much better. If they hear you cussing at night, they visit you in the morning when you are sober and cane you. It was worse before (Thandanani village, male FGD participant).

That woman (pointing to the chairlady of Ward 2 PC) was brave. She spoke to these 'crocodiles' at the center, these machete gangs, and it helped. We can now walk freely at night without fear. Her bravery helped a lot, and this woman sorted out this issue for us. We no longer walked outside once it became dark. Some of us were afraid to go with her. We just saw her and others leaving in cars to look for these people who 'machete' others (Thandanani village, male FGD, Ward 1).

When questioned discreetly, the woman refrained from offering a definitive response and dismissed the individual as unreliable. Despite this, none of the gentlemen present disputed this claim. It is possible that the speaker exaggerated the story for effect; however, the overall accuracy of the narrative may still be valid. Regardless of the specifics, the woman was likely responsible for instigating the situation.

The effectiveness of women as peacebuilders in wards 1 and 2

The above discussion illustrates that women can be very effective peacemakers if given the opportunity. Women in Gangabezi village attributed their ability to hold the police accountable to the program's effects. Speaking about how things were before the work of the committee began, concerning police [in]action on reported cases, one lady had this to say, The peace committee helps a lot in bringing awareness because people were afraid to speak their minds. However, they helped to enlighten them so that they could speak about their issues openly. They were afraid of what might happen to them if they spoke the truth. Another one chipped in, Yes, they opened our minds indeed, now people can speak freely, [saying] "You police officers have been bribed," they no longer hold back; they tell them the truth. They no longer fear speaking, even in the presence of the police. Emthonjeni must continue to teach us because they help us a lot.

The women at Mpumelelo village spoke of a case of a young man who had been 'macheted', and when following up, the police officers who had attended the case claimed that the docket had gone missing. They reported them to the officer-in-charge, after which the police officers returned to take fresh statements.

According to the councilor for Ward 2, this sort of pressure on the police had resulted in the arrest and conviction of a machete gang, which had recently been sentenced to periods ranging from 18-20 years in prison. This

outcome seems to have helped reduce the amount of violence and sense of impunity with which these gangs acted. Participants also indicated that when a case is dragging on, they follow up with the police bosses with the help of EWF. As one of them put it, “we go to those terrifying offices with the help of Emthonjeni.”

The strength of the intervention seems to lie in its appeal to all community formations, at least to those interested in peace and order. The program is largely rooted in the community, and there seems to be a high level of community ownership. While there is a ward PC that offers oversight and support, village PCs appear to be autonomous and free to act in accordance with their specific contexts. As noted earlier, the composition of some PCs differs slightly depending on the need. The relationship with the villageheads is seamless, and the PCs complement the villageheads’ work. However, the nature of conflicts and violence requires skills beyond what they would normally deal with in the absence of artisanal mining-inspired problems. The villageheads interviewed did not seem to be threatened by the PCs’ work, as most were part of them. They expressed gratitude for the support they received. They still have the usual cases coming to their courts. PCs also reported that there were some cases that they had referred to the villageheads, and when such cases were being tried, they also participated in the process. However, interviewees from most Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) indicated that they preferred to have their issues dealt with by the PCs, as they were more effective than the police and, sometimes, even the traditional leaders, in addressing their concerns. Additionally, women’s ability to set up early warning systems after training has been vital in reducing violent conflicts through their early responses.

The fact that the communities seem to have accepted the leadership and role of women in the peacemaking process perhaps speaks to the success and integrity of women-led interventions. The men appeared at ease to be led by women, with no hint of any patriarchal superiority complex that has been said to be synonymous with African societies.

Challenges

Time constraints and competing responsibilities

While women in Wards 1 and 2 are doing an excellent job as peacebuilders, they face challenges and constraints that hinder their optimum effectiveness. First and most importantly, women have many responsibilities that make it difficult for them to dedicate the optimum time required for their peacebuilding initiatives. Their multiple gender roles ensure that they are responsible for home chores and that their children are cared for. Some of them are either employed or have their own income-generating projects, and they must also participate in community activities and other NGOs’ programs.

Resource constraints

Members of the ward PCs noted their struggles with resources to fund their activities. While they mentioned that the availability of mobile phones was of great help, they nevertheless pointed out that data and airtime costs, which are now beyond their reach, were constraints on their activities, as they could not recharge frequently. They indicated that they had received some support from EWF, but it was less than the present demand. In addition, they were often called to attend to cases in areas far from their homes, and they had to use their personal resources to get there. Nevertheless, members of the ward PCs showed commitment to their work, which they viewed as essential for their communities and appeared to enjoy doing.

Insecurity and feelings of inadequacy

Members of the PCs reported that they sometimes hesitated to approach certain individuals for fear of reprisals, usually when dealing with outsiders. Sometimes, they found ways around this, but at times, it stalled their peace

efforts. For instance, the PC at Mpumelelo, which is composed of only women, said that when attending to potentially dangerous incidents, they would ask men from their community to accompany them.

Although members received training in community leadership, conflict mapping, citizen journalism, conflict prevention, management resolution, and transformation, they expressed feelings of inadequacy in certain situations. However, they indicated that they often referred difficult cases to EWF for assistance, and external resource persons (such as lawyers) were also available to them.

Discussion

The most significant insight from this study is that the women's peace committees were generally effective in addressing conflicts and finding peaceful solutions to community issues when there was a shared cultural foundation for their moral authority. These committees were more successful when both parties involved in the conflict or engaged in antisocial behavior were local community members. However, they were less effective in cases involving outsiders, such as artisanal miners from outside the community. In such situations, men were often called upon to take on a leading role in addressing the offenders, but this was still done under the guidance of female peace committee leaders.

Despite having undergone capacity-building workshops in peacebuilding and conflict management, one village PC resorted to using force to maintain peace, thus deviating from the training and goals of developing and maintaining social cohesion. The predominant focus of the EWF program was on women; therefore, it is conceivable that men may not have received the same in-depth training on peace and conflict resolution as the female participants. Consequently, men may have defaulted to using violence to resolve conflicts, which is often considered an acceptable approach.

The question of using force to 'maintain peace' is contentious. Peace maintained by force is what Galtung (1964) called negative peace, the absence of visible violence or war. Paradoxically, almost all other villages envied the Gangabezi village Peace Committee for its ability to tame the violence of the machete-wielding gangs. We heard of its work even before arriving at their village. In fact, there seems to have been a general leaning towards the use of violence, such as corporal punishment, as a form of peace enforcement tool or discipline. We have reported above how the peace committee in Vusisizwe village threatened a 14-year-old wayward girl with corporal punishment. There seems to be a contradiction between the peace committees appearing not to have any qualms with the use of violence to maintain peace, and yet working against the violence happening in the community. While the desired goal for peacebuilding should be positive peace (the presence of conflict resolution mechanisms that allow for equitable and fair access to justice and power), how do communities address this impunity, rowdiness, and blatant disregard for human life and the law, perpetrated by artisanal miners, which has now become a norm even within the villages? In view of their circumstances and exposure, perhaps where violence is prevalent, negative peace is viewed as a lesser evil than violence and chaos. It is also important to note that this PC that resorted to force is male-dominated, and as such, social cohesion might be elusive and peace ephemeral. To foster peace in Wards 1 and 2 of Insiza, it is crucial to prioritize non-violent approaches and promote social cohesion as alternatives to conflict resolution. Although nonviolence may not be a panacea for all situations, studies have shown that it can be more effective than violence in resolving conflicts and creating a conducive environment for peacebuilding efforts (Chinoweth & Stephan, 2011). The concept of conflict transformation proposed by Lederach (2003) is an ideal approach for transforming destructive conflicts into constructive opportunities for growth and development. As such, peace committees should strive to promote non-violent approaches and social cohesion to move towards positive peace.

It has been posited that patriarchal culture accompanied by restrictive gendered norms, lack of exposure to peacebuilding instruments, lack of confidence and poor sense of self, lack of support for each other, household responsibilities, and resources are some of the challenges and obstacles women tend to face in their quest to build peace (Cardona *et. al.*, 2012; Chitando, 2009; Machakanja, 2016; Masunungure & Mbwirire, 2016; Simpson & Assaad, 2022). The study findings show that for women in Wards 2 and 3 in Insiza District, patriarchy and its related effects did not appear to be a significant barrier. As indicated above, the PCs at the village level were predominantly women-led and controlled, although men were members of some of them. Of particular interest was the PC in Gangabezi Village, which, although its foot soldiers were men, the men reported to the female leaders. At the ward level, peace committees are entirely composed of and led by female members.

However, the findings indicate that, at least in as far as peacebuilding was concerned, local men had no problem being led by women, and fully supported women's work and recognized the good work the women were doing. As the area is a rural setup, one would have expected some resistance from men to the work of these committees. On the contrary, one councilor indicated that the community (including men) sometimes preferred to have peace committees deal with their issues rather than any other dispute resolution mechanism available to them. Even people with issues that required police or villagehead intervention seemed to prefer their issues to be submitted through peace committees.

The success of these PCs may be attributed to several factors. First, almost all members received extensive training in conflict resolution and peacebuilding. Several workshops were conducted, including one on violence, early warning systems, and mitigation. Furthermore, EWF provided support for the committee members; members were able to request assistance whenever they encountered situations beyond their abilities. As noted earlier, patriarchy did not seem to be an issue in these two wards, at least regarding the

PCs' activities. Men respected women's leadership and efforts to address conflicts and violence in these communities. These communities appear to have transcended most of the usual patriarchal and cultural obstacles that normally impede women's effective participation in community activities and in leadership roles. However, it is possible that the higher status of some women added gravity to their peacebuilding roles. As noted by Gizelis (2009), peace efforts tend to be more effective when women have higher economic and social status because their voices are easily heard and their involvement is easily accepted. Several of these women have their own businesses, including small mines and retail shops. However, these women were in the minority, and most women were housewives. Therefore, this may not be a complete explanation for their success. Another possible explanation, as intimated earlier, is that women drew their moral authority as mothers from the shared cultural underpinnings and understanding, which allowed them to be quite successful, especially among the youth.

It is noteworthy that certain female members of the peace committee seemed to grapple with self-doubt about their aptitude for resolving disputes, an observation that aligns with the findings of Chitando (2009), Cardona *et al.* (2012) and Machakanja (2016) in their respective studies. Despite this, the community held them in high esteem and displayed confidence in their ability to address conflict. Both male and female participants from various villages emphasized the influence of the PCs and believed that without them, the level of violence and conflict in the community would be significantly higher. It is worth mentioning that the community expressed a preference for involving female peacebuilders in their affairs. It is crucial to acknowledge that communities possess the inherent capacity to address their own conflicts and may only require encouragement to trust their abilities.

Conclusion

This study examined the consequences of women's efforts to resolve and address hostilities and disputes resulting from mining activities in Wards 1 and 2 of the Insiza District, Zimbabwe. The Emthonjeni Women's Forum (EWF) initiative established 12 peace committees with 120 female peacebuilders in the area, which is characterized by high unemployment rates, subsistence farming, and the presence of illegal artisanal mining groups, such as the violent gangsters known as *aMabhambadzi*. Peace committees collaborate with the community to recognize and evaluate conflicts, develop platforms for conflict resolution, establish prevention mechanisms, and establish warning systems. This study evaluated the effectiveness of women as strategic partners in the EWF's Peacebuilding and Social Cohesion project and contributes to the understanding of women's roles in peacebuilding in rural mining regions that are plagued by violence and lawlessness.

With the inception of the women as strategic partners in the peacebuilding program, particularly the resultant formation of women-led peace committees, all research participants reported a noticeable positive change. Women have taken the lead in dealing with many conflicts and violence caused by the presence of artisanal mining in Wards 1 and 2. Successful interventions range from mitigating violence in shopping centers to resolving conflicts within families. Stakeholders such as the DDC, ZRP, Ministry of Women and Youth Affairs, and traditional leaders indicated their satisfaction with the work of the peace committees. Interviewees from most Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) indicated that they preferred to have their issues dealt with by PCs and that PCs were more effective than the police. Several reasons may have contributed to the success of women appear to have had in Insiza. The most significant insight from this study is that the women's peace committees were generally effective in addressing conflicts and finding peaceful solutions to community issues when there was a shared cultural foundation for their moral authority. These committees were more successful when both parties involved in the conflict or engaged in antisocial behavior were local community members. However, they were less effective in cases involving outsiders, such as artisanal miners from outside the community.

The results of this study may not be applicable to other areas because of the unique factors present in Wards 1 and 2 of Insiza. However, it provides valuable insights into the important role that female peacebuilders can play in creating peaceful grassroots communities. These two wards have peculiar circumstances that may differ from other mining areas, as the consequences of lawlessness extend beyond the mining areas of the wards and affect their daily lives in their homes.

This study was conducted at the intervention stage of the program, and it may be beneficial to evaluate its long-term effects to determine its sustainability. It could be advantageous to explore the methods through which this community transcends patriarchal obstacles and whether this extends to other aspects of community involvement, beyond peacebuilding. Finally, a comparative analysis of similar interventions at other locations could yield valuable insights for practical applications.

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